

Oxidation of some α -Amino Acids by Trichloroisocyanuric Acid : A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

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The oxidation of five α -amino acids, viz. glycine (gly), alanine (ala), valine (val), phenylalanine (phala) and leucine (leu) by trichloroisocyanuric acid (TCICA) in acetic acid-water mixture containing sulphuric acid, follows the rate law,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_d K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [S]_T}{([DCICA] + K_{h1})(K_2 + [H^+]) + K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [S]_T}$$

The reactions are dependent on the permittivity of the medium. The order of reactivity is gly < ala < val < phala < leu. A plot of $\log k_d$ against E_s is linear ($r = 0.985$) with a ρ value of -0.63 . A mechanism involving complexation between HOCl generated from TCICA and the unprotonated substrate molecule has been proposed. Activation parameters have been computed.

Trichloroisocyanuric acid (TCICA) or 1,3,5-trichloro-1(*H*),3(*H*),5(*H*)-triazine-2,4,6-trione is a well-known chlorine donor¹. Its hydrolytic reaction with water produces HOCl which itself and its protonated form H_2O^+Cl are potent oxidising species. TCICA oxidation of α -hydroxy acids², ketones³, sulphacetamide⁴ has been documented. Preliminary runs on the oxidation of some α -amino acids by this oxidant revealed smooth kinetics and hence an attempt has been made to establish the kinetic orders, throw light on the mechanism and compare the results with the oxidation by other *N*-halo compounds⁵.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of phala, gly, ala, val and leu by TCICA in acetic acid-water (1:9, v/v) were studied under varying conditions: [TCICA] ($3.22-13.51 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³), [Substrate] ($1.25-10.00$ mol dm⁻³) and $[H_2SO_4]_t$ ($0.25-2.00$ mol dm⁻³). In each run the plot of $\log [TCICA]_t$ versus time was found to be linear upto three half-lives indicating pseudo-first order kinetics. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was also

found to be invariant over a four-fold variation of initial [TCICA]. The k_{obs} values were found to increase marginally (Table 1) with an increase in [Substrate]. For different substrates they were also found to be divergent. The $k_{\text{obs}}/[S]$ values showed a diminishing trend with increasing [Substrate] pointing to Michaelis-Menton behaviour. The double reciprocal or Lineweaver-Burk plot was linear for each substrate with definite intercepts on the reciprocal rate axis from which the decomposition constants (k_d) were calculated at different temperatures.

An increase in the concentration of H_2SO_4 retarded the rate. Plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [H^+]$ were linear with slopes -1.37 , -1.09 , -1.20 , -1.14 and -0.93 for leu, phala, val, ala and gly respectively.

The reactions were also found to be dependent on the permittivity of the medium. Increasing proportions of acetic acid retarded the rate. With [phala] = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, [TCICA] = 0.74×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ and at 30°, the $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s⁻¹) values at 10, 20,

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AT VARYING [SUBSTRATE] AND DECOMPOSITION CONSTANTS

[TCICA] = 0.74×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, solvent : HOAc-Water (1 : 9)

Substrate	Temp. °C	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹) at 10^3 [Substrate]				
		1.25	2.50	5.00 mol dm ⁻³	10.00	$\times 10^4 k_d$ (s ⁻¹)
Phala	30	8.01	8.23	8.48	9.00	8.89
	40	23.42	28.49	29.70	33.30	34.47
	50	38.00	40.90	43.44	45.45	46.07
Gly	30	0.54	0.56	0.60	0.64	0.64
	40	1.09	1.28	1.35	1.54	1.56
	50	3.33	3.49	4.34	4.55	4.66
Ala	30	3.61	4.51	4.82	5.74	5.90
	40	10.76	13.62	15.28	17.20	18.39
	50	17.45	21.78	25.13	32.20	32.82
Val	30	4.84	5.34	5.81	7.45	7.04
	40	12.43	24.62	18.03	20.80	21.66
	50	20.69	25.45	26.50	33.30	33.16
Leu	30	7.29	10.09	10.27	15.89	15.46
	40	16.22	21.98	27.11	36.40	39.22
	50	27.45	32.27	47.98	57.14	61.45

30 and 50% acetic acid-water mixtures (v/v) were 8.48, 7.77, 5.50 and 2.04 respectively. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $(D-1)/(2D + 1)$ was found to be linear pointing to a dipole-dipole type of reaction.

To study the effect of temperature, the k_{obs} values at varying [Substrate] were determined and the decomposition constants (k_d) calculated from the intercepts of the double reciprocal plots are shown in Table 1. The Arrhenius plots of $\log k_d$ versus $1/T$ are linear. The computed activation parameters are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 30°

Substrate	E_a KJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger KJ mol ⁻¹	$\log_{10} A$	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Phala	67.38	64.86	8.56	-89.43
Gly	80.83	78.31	9.73	-66.95
Ala	70.00	67.48	8.83	-84.18
Val	63.32	60.80	7.76	-104.76
Leu	56.36	53.84	6.90	-121.19

The $\log_{10} A$ values are much less than that expected for bimolecular reaction indicating the formation of a complex prior to the reaction proper. This is also supported by large negative values of ΔS^\ddagger . The plot of $\log_{10} A$ versus $1/\sqrt{E_a}$

is linear. The isokinetic plot⁶ of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger is linear with isokinetic temperature $\beta = 430$ K.

Hydrolysis of TCICA¹ under the present experimental condition can be shown as

The hydrolytic equilibria show that the concentration of monochloroisocyanuric acid (MCICA) and isocyanuric acid (ICA) would be negligible in acid medium as the factors ($K_{h1} K_{h2} K_{h3}$) and ($K_{h1} K_{h2}$) are negligible as compared to K_{h1} . Hence the first stage of hydrolysis seems to be kinetically important. Further, the inverse dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ may be traced to the protonation equilibria involving the amino acids. In most acidic region it is the conjugate acid (SH^+) that predominates. Since the H^+ dependence is inverse, the unprotonated molecule may be taken to be the reacting species.

From the first order kinetics in [TCICA], fractional order in [Substrate], inverse dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ and dipolar nature of the reaction as

evident from the study of solvent effect, the following sequence of steps as shown below is proposed :

The total substrate concentration is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\text{S}]_T &= [\text{S}] + [\text{SH}^+] \\
 &= [\text{S}] + [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] / K_2 \\
 &= [\text{S}] \left\{ 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2} \right\} \\
 \text{Hence, } [\text{S}] &= \frac{K_2 [\text{S}]_T}{K_2 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The total TCICA concentration is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\text{TCICA}]_T &= [\text{TCICA}]_f + [\text{HOCl}] + [\text{C}] \\
 &= \frac{[\text{DCICA}] [\text{HOCl}]}{K_{h1}} + \\
 &\quad [\text{HOCl}] + K_3 [\text{HOCl}] [\text{S}] \\
 &= [\text{MOC}] \\
 &\quad \left\{ \frac{[\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1} + K_{h1} K_3 [\text{S}]}{K_{h1}} \right\} \\
 \text{Hence, } [\text{HOCl}] &= \frac{K_{h1} [\text{TCICA}]_T}{[\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1} + K_{h1} K_3 [\text{S}]} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Hence, } [\text{C}] &= K_3 [\text{S}] [\text{HOCl}] \\
 &= \frac{K_{h1} K_3 [\text{S}] [\text{TCICA}]_T}{[\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1} + K_{h1} K_3 [\text{S}]}
 \end{aligned}$$

Utilising the value of [S] from equation (1), we get

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T [\text{TCICA}]_T}{([\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1})(K_2 + [\text{H}^+]) + K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, rate

$$-\frac{d[\text{TCICA}]_T}{dt} = -\frac{d[\text{C}]}{dt} = k_d [\text{C}]$$

$$= \frac{k_d K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T [\text{TCICA}]_T}{([\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1})(K_2 + [\text{H}^+]) + K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{or } k_{\text{obs}} &= -\frac{d[\text{TCICA}]_T}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{TCICA}]_T} \\
 &= \frac{k_d K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T}{([\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1})(K_2 + [\text{H}^+]) + K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T} \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

This can be rearranged to the form,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{([\text{DCICA}] + K_{h1})(K_2 + [\text{H}^+])}{k_d K_{h1} K_2 K_3 [\text{S}]_T} + \frac{1}{k_d} \quad (6)$$

The above equation explains all the experimental facts observed.

Contrary to the earlier observations^{7,8}, the order of reactivity among the substrates is leu > phala > val > ala > gly. In the oxidation of the above substrates by lead tetraacetate⁹ and *N*-bromoacetamide^{7,8}, the greater reactivity of phenylalanine as compared to leucine was explained by treating the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ group as a strongly electron-releasing group. The abnormal reactivity of phenylalanine was also thought to be due to alpha-effect¹⁰. However in the present study, the plot of $\log k_d$ values against the E_s values⁶ is linear ($r = 0.985$) with a slope of -0.63 indicating the steric effect due to substituents rather than the polar effect being the important controlling factor.

Experimental

TCICA (Riedal, G.R.) preserved in dark, was used as such. The concentration of all the amino acids (Loba, G.R.) was determined by Sorensen formol titration. Sulphuric acid (AnalaR) was used after standardisation. The progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating the unreacted TCICA iodometrically¹¹ in accordance with the equation,

The rate constants in replicates were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. Under the experimental conditions, the self-decomposition of TCICA was negligibly small and the rate constants were practically unaltered under aerated and deaerated atmosphere.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by thermostating reaction mixtures containing known excess of [TCICA] over that of [Substrate] at constant [H₂SO₄] and solvent composition. Nearly three moles of substrate were consumed per mole of TCICA. The stoichiometric equation appears to be,

The aldehyde products were identified following the reported procedures⁷.

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